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Research Article

**IN NORMAL PREGNANCY THE IMPORTANCE OF
TRANSVAGINAL SONOGRAPHY IN ASSESSING THE
CERVICAL LENGTH CHANGES AND THEIR CORRELATION**¹Dr. Maria Imtiaz, ²Dr. Asma Asif Rana, ³Dr. Almas Adil,¹Fatima Jinnah Medical College, Lahore²THQ Hospital Nowshera Virkan, Gujranwala³Quaid-e-Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur**Abstract**

Objective: For determining the cervical length the gold standard investigation is Trans-vaginal ultrasound (TVS). The purpose of this analysis was to investigate changes in cervical length during normal pregnancy confirmed by TVS.

Study Design: An epidemiological study.

Place and Duration: In the Gynecology and Obstetrics Unit II in Collaboration with Radiology Department of Services Hospital, Lahore for one year duration from April 2017 to April 2018.

Methodology: This epidemiological study was conducted in 150 pregnant women. In normal pregnancies, cervical length changes were analyzed by TVS in 3 trimesters of pregnancy. 8 to 37 weeks was studied population gestational age. For statistical analysis, Anova and Chi-square tests were used.

Results: The cervical length in the second trimester was minimal (26 mm) and the mean cervical length (40.72 mm). The cervical length in the first trimester was maximum (56 mm) and the mean cervical length was (39.03 mm). Under 20 years of age pregnant females have mean cervical length as shortest (37.83 mm) and in the age group above 35 years longest up to 40 mm.

Conclusion: Transvaginal ultrasound is beneficial for evaluation of cervical length and treatment of cervical insufficiency and premature births.

Key Words: Cervical length, normal pregnancy, Transvaginal ultrasound.

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INTRODUCTION:

During pregnancy, in preventing premature birth and protecting the fetus the cervix plays an important role. The cervical enlargement or shortening and the treatment of cervical insufficiency are very important in preterm deliveries. In addition, shortening of the cervical length increases the risk of premature birth. Today, transvaginal ultrasound is very important in the cervical insufficiency diagnosis and is a safe and acceptable method in cervical examination compared with abdominal or perineal ultrasound and Gold standard for cervical research. The term transvaginal ultrasound showed that the delivery of the cervix in the 1st 30 weeks, but gradually decreased in the 3rd trimester. The period of birth is usually confirmed in the 1st four months of gestation, then it is gradually shortened by the 8th term and there is an inverse association between preterm birth and cervical length. In one analysis, cervical length was calculated at 24th and 28th gestational weeks and cervical lengths showed that progressively shortened females had a risk of premature birth. In other analysis, the cervical length calculated by transvaginal ultrasound was measured in 2 groups by obstetricians, which were calculated as 32 and 18 mm, respectively. In 14-22 gestation week's cervical length was recorded in another study. Cervical length was calculated at weeks and 11-14. In 22-24 weeks, cervical length and preterm births were equal. Therefore, since cervical length shortening enhances the risk of premature birth, the patients' clinical evaluation with proven cervical insufficiency is necessary (measurement of cervical length by transvaginal ultrasound).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This epidemiological study was held in the Gynecology and Obstetrics Unit II in Collaboration with Radiology Department of Services Hospital, Lahore for one year duration from April 2017 to April 2018. 150 pregnant women were included in the epidemiological study. The cervical length changes were calculated by transvaginal ultrasound by the radiologist in three trimesters of normal pregnancy (approximately 50 females in every trimester). In our population, 8 to 37 weeks is the mean gestational age. Women having multiple pregnancies, curettage and dilatation history, premature delivery, cervical abnormalities and cerclage cases were not selected for the analysis. Into 3 age groups, Patients were divided. In 1st under 20 years of age, in 2nd group 20-35 years and in 3rd group females of 35 years were included. For the analysis, Chi-square tests, Descriptive statistics tables and Anova test were used. All subjects were explained the details of the study and agreed were allowed to participate in this analysis.

RESULTS:

As shown in Table I, the 26 mm was the minimum cervical length in the second trimester and the average cervical length was 41.02 mm while the cervical length was maximum 56 mm and in 1st trimester the mean of minimum cervical length was 39.03 mm.

Table-I: Cervical length in 3 trimesters

<i>Duration of pregnancy(weeks)</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Mean (millimeter)</i>	<i>Minimum (millimeter)</i>	<i>Maximum (millimeter)</i>
8-14	51	39	28	56
15-28	51	40.7	26	52
29-37	48	39.3	27	52

Table II shows that the cervical length 50 mm or less was most commonly observed and the cervical length of less than 30 mm is rare.

Table-II: Distribution of cervical length in 3 trimesters

<i>Duration of pregnancy (weeks)</i>	<i>Cervical length (millimeter)</i>	<i>Percentage of frequency</i>
8-14	<30	3.9
	<40	56.9
	<50	94.1
15-28	<30	9.8
	<40	37.3
	<50	88.2
29-37	<30	4.2
	<40	54.2
	<50	93.8

The types of cervical length are given in Table III.

Table-III: Cervical length based on the previous deliveries

<i>Type of delivery</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Mean (millimeter)</i>	<i>Minimum (millimeter)</i>	<i>Maximum (millimeter)</i>
Normal delivery	26	41.9	29	56
Cesarean section	26	39.5	28	52
Nullipar	98	39.1	26	52

The majority of the population studied and the minimum surgical length were observed in nulliparas and the maximum cervical length was observed at normal birth. Age groups are shown in Table IV.

Table-IV: Cervical length in different age group

<i>Age groups(year)</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Mean (millimeter)</i>	<i>Minimum (millimeter)</i>	<i>Maximum (millimeter)</i>
<20	6	37.8	26	46
20-35	135	39.7	26	56
>35	9	40	29	50

Between the ages of 21-36 Group had the least cervical length while groups between 20 and 35 years of age had the maximum cervical length. The minimum and maximum mean cervical length was minimum in the age group under the age of 20 years

and maximum in the age group of 35 years of age, respectively. The cervical length mean was assessed according to parity, with a mean cervical length of 38.49 and 40.79 mm in women with parity 1 and parity greater than 1, respectively.

DISCUSSION:

The cervical length was calculated in 3 trimesters, which proves that in the first trimester maximum cervical length was noted, but there was no significant difference between the three phases in terms of statistical significance ($p = 0.38$). In a survey, the cervical length was measured with transvaginal ultrasound at weeks was 20-25. It showed the maximum cervical length in weeks. Another study showed that cervical length did not change significantly. The duration of the cervix in the first 16 weeks of gestation was almost constant, and the mean cervical length corresponding to the findings of our study was also assessed in 3 age groups and no vast variation was observed ($P = 0.77$). One analysis shows that on cervical length there is no effect of age and this point was related to our analysis. The cervical length mean was determined depending on parity and in multiparas it was longer compared to nulliparas and the variation was significant statistically ($P = 0.04$). In other analysis, it was seen that the length of the cervix was higher in women than in parity women who had parity before cesarean section or parity in first trimester; this was consistent with the findings of our study. Another study showed that there was no static difference between multipara, cervical length and nullipara incompatible with our analysis. Cervical length was determined according to type of birth and no static variation was observed ($P = 0.19$). In one study, it was noted that birth types had an insignificant effect on cervical length according to our findings.

CONCLUSION:

This study examined 150 pregnant women during normal gestational period and confirmed the previous analysis results on cervical length due to parity and gravity. Management and detection of cervical insufficiency and preterm labor due to cervical length changes diagnosed in transvaginal ultrasonography were found to be very useful.

REFERENCES:

1. Souka, Athena P., Ioannis Papastefanou, Athanasios Pilalis, Dimitrios Kassanos, and George Papadopoulos. "Implementation of universal screening for preterm delivery by mid-trimester cervical length measurement." *Ultrasound in Obstetrics & Gynecology* (2018).
2. Oi, R., Miyasaka, N., Yamashita, T. and Adachi, T., 2018. Associations of temporal changes in cervical length and lower uterine segment length with spontaneous preterm delivery risk: a prospective study of 727 Japanese women. *Journal of Medical Ultrasonics*, pp.1-7.
3. Gascón, A., Goya, M., Mendoza, M., Garcia, A., Higuera, T., Calero, I., Avilés, M., Sánchez, M.A., Llurba, E., Cabero, L. and Carreras, E., 2018. Intraobserver and interobserver variability in first-trimester transvaginal ultrasound cervical length. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine*, pp.1-6.
4. Rosen, Hadar, Liran Hiersch, Howie Freeman, Jon Barrett, and Nir Melamed. "The role of serial measurements of cervical length in asymptomatic women with triplet pregnancy." *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine* 31, no. 6 (2018): 713-719.
5. Weitzner, O., Biron-Shental, T., Daykan, Y., Ezra, O. and Markovitch, O., 2018. Can sonographic measurements and changes in cervical length during pregnancy predict preterm labour in an asymptomatic low-risk population?. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine*, pp.1-6.
6. Schnettler, William T., Shwetha Manoharan, and Kathleen L. Smith. "426: Transvaginal sonographic assessment following cervical pessary placement for preterm birth prevention." *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology* 218, no. 1 (2018): S259.
7. Lim, Kenneth, Kimberly Butt, and Joan M. Crane. "No. 257-Ultrasonographic Cervical Length Assessment in Predicting Preterm Birth in Singleton Pregnancies." *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Canada* 40, no. 2 (2018): e151-e164. Lim, K., Butt, K., & Crane, J. M. (2018). No. 257-Ultrasonographic Cervical Length Assessment in Predicting Preterm Birth in Singleton Pregnancies. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Canada*, 40(2), e151-e164.
8. Connolly, Katherine A., Luciana Vieira, Elizabeth Yoselevsky, and Joanne Stone. "91: Variation in transvaginal cervical length over time during single transvaginal exam." *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology* 218, no. 1 (2018): S66. Connolly, K. A., Vieira, L., Yoselevsky, E., & Stone, J. (2018). 91: Variation in transvaginal cervical length over time during single transvaginal exam. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 218(1), S66.
9. Baños N, Julià C, Lorente N, Ferrero S, Cobo T, Gratacos E, Palacio M. Mid-Trimester Cervical Consistency Index and Cervical Length to Predict Spontaneous Preterm Birth in a High-Risk Population. *American Journal of Perinatology Reports*. 2018 Jan;8(01):e43-50.
10. Campbell, Stuart. "Prevention of spontaneous preterm birth: universal cervical length assessment and vaginal progesterone in women

- with a short cervix: time for action!." (2018): 151-158. Campbell, Stuart. "Prevention of spontaneous preterm birth: universal cervical length assessment and vaginal progesterone in women with a short cervix: time for action!." (2018): 151-158.
11. Pruksanusak N, Sawaddisan R, Kor-anantakul O, Suntharasaj T, Suwanrath C, Geater A. Comparison of reliability between uterocervical angle and cervical length measurements by various experienced operators using transvaginal ultrasound. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine*. 2018 Sep 20:1-8.
 12. Norman M, Cnattingius S, Vixner L, Waldenström U. Authors' reply re: Advanced maternal age increases the risk of very preterm birth irrespective of parity—a population based register study. *BJOG: An International Journal of Obstetrics & Gynaecology*. 2018 Apr;125(5):634-.
 13. Martell, Bridget, Dana B. DiBenedetti, Herman Weiss, Xiaolei Zhou, Maria Reynolds, Vincenzo Berghella, and Sonia S. Hassan. "Screening and treatment for short cervical length in pregnancy: a physician survey in the United States." *Archives of gynecology and obstetrics* 297, no. 3 (2018): 601-611.
 14. Khandelwal, Ronak, Purvi Patel, Dipa Pitre, Tosha Sheth, and Nandita Maitra. "Comparison of Cervical Length Measured by Transvaginal Ultrasonography and Bishop Score in Predicting Response to Labor Induction." *The Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology of India* 68, no. 1 (2018): 51-57.
 15. Wang, Liang. "Value of serial cervical length measurement in prediction of spontaneous preterm birth in post-conization pregnancy without short mid-trimester cervix." *Scientific reports* 8, no. 1 (2018): 15305.